

FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMERS' PURCHASE DECISIONS FOR OFFICE FASHION: A CASE STUDY IN HANOI

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Abstract

To examine the factors influencing consumers' purchase decisions for office fashion in Hanoi, the research team surveyed 275 customers who had purchased office fashion products in Hanoi and analyzed the collected data using SMARTPLS software. The findings reveal that all five factors examined exert an influence on consumers' purchase decisions for office fashion. Among these, the factor "Perceived Behavioral Control" (HV) has the strongest impact on purchase decisions, with an effect size of 0.543, followed by "Subjective Norms" (CCQ) with an effect size of 0.164. The two factors "Perceived Ease of Use" and "Perceived Usefulness of Office Fashion" strongly influence the mediating factor "Attitude toward Office Fashion", which in turn affects consumers' purchase decisions for office fashion, with an effect size of 0.149. Based on the analysis results, the research team offers several points of discussion aimed at attracting office fashion consumers, thereby contributing to an improved working environment and corporate image.

Keywords: Influencing Factors, Office Fashion, SMARTPLS Software, Hanoi.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern working environment, office fashion increasingly plays an important role in conveying professional demeanor, personal image, and corporate identity. Particularly in Hanoi — a major economic, political, and cultural center of the country — the demand for office fashion products has been growing, especially among young workers, civil servants, and office employees. The rapid development of the fashion industry, coupled with swiftly changing consumer trends, poses an urgent requirement for businesses to accurately understand the factors influencing consumers' purchasing behavior.

In practice, consumers' purchase decisions for office fashion are influenced by a variety of factors, such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude toward the product, subjective norms (social influence), and perceived behavioral control (the ability to actively engage in purchasing).

A clear understanding of these factors enables businesses to better position their products, optimize marketing strategies, and effectively develop their brands.

This study aims to examine the factors influencing consumers' purchase decisions for office fashion in Hanoi. Using a desk research approach, the research team reviewed relevant concepts and theoretical foundations pertaining to motivation, attitude, and purchasing behavior for office fashion. Subsequently, a sociological survey was conducted by designing a questionnaire on Google Forms and distributing it directly to consumers in Hanoi using a convenient and random sampling method. A total of 275 responses were collected, including 249 female consumers (91%) and 26 male consumers (9%).

Consumers' decisions to purchase office fashion are influenced by five independent factors, including three direct factors and two factors mediated through an intermediate factor. The survey data were processed and validated using SmartPLS software, which assessed the influence level of each factor on the purchasing behavior of office fashion consumers in Hanoi. Based on the analysis results, the research team presents several discussion points and recommendations to attract consumers to purchase and experience office fashion products, thereby contributing to an improved working environment and enhanced corporate image.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK, RESEARCH MODEL, AND HYPOTHESES

2.1. Office Fashion and Consumer Behavior

Office fashion refers to clothing designed to be appropriate for workplace settings, particularly in offices, agencies, and organizations with a high level of professionalism. Such attire must not only ensure modesty and elegance but also reflect the wearer's personal style, professionalism, and serious demeanor. Office fashion serves not only the individual's aesthetic needs but also contributes to projecting professionalism, seriousness, and the brand image of each individual and organization in the workplace.

Consumer behavior encompasses the actions, decisions, and thought processes of customers when searching for, selecting, or using products or services. The decision to choose and use office fashion in a work setting (*office fashion purchase decision*) refers to the consumer's choice and use of office fashion in professional environments. Consumers' decisions to select office fashion are influenced by factors such as attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

2.2. Selected Research Models on Behavioral Intention

2.2.1. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), developed by Ajzen (1991) as an extension of the original Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), incorporates *perceived behavioral control* alongside *attitude* and *subjective norms* as factors influencing consumers' behavioral intentions.

The TPB is a model that explains human behavior based on individuals' intentions to perform a specific action. According to the TPB, an individual's intention to perform a behavior is influenced by three main factors: *attitude*, *subjective norms*, and *perceived behavioral control*. These factors interact and jointly predict an individual's intention to engage in the behavior, which in turn directly influences actual behavior. The TPB thus provides a clearer understanding of the mechanisms through which psychological and social factors impact human behavior.

Figure 1: The theoretical model of planned behavior – TPB

Source: Ajzen, 1991

2.2.2. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis in 1989, illustrates the extent to which an individual is willing to exert effort and intends to use a new technology. The decision to adopt and use a technology depends on the individual's intention to use that technology.

Figure 2: Technology acceptance model TAM

Source: David, 1989

The intention to use a technology depends on the user's attitude toward the technology. The user's attitude, in turn, is influenced by two factors: (1) The user's perceived usefulness of the technology. (2) The user's perceived ease of use of the technology.

2.2.3. C-TAM-TPB model

The C-TAM-TPB model (*Combined Theory of Planned Behavior*) is an extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), designed to explain human behavior based on intention and social perception.

The combined C-TAM-TPB model was introduced by Taylor and Todd (1995). In this model, Taylor and Todd supplemented the original TAM by incorporating two additional key factors: subjective norms and perceived behavioral control. Accordingly, the C-TAM-TPB model identifies three main factors influencing behavioral intention: (1) attitude, (2) subjective norms, and (3) perceived behavioral control. Within this framework, the variable attitude is influenced by the two variables perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, while perceived usefulness also directly affects behavioral intention.

Figure 3: C-TAM-TP model

Source: Taylor & Todd (1995)

- (1) Subjective norms refer to “an individual’s perception of social pressure to perform or not to perform a behavior.” When an individual perceives stronger social expectations for a certain behavior, they tend to conform to those expectations and perform the behavior. Research by Hartwick & Barki (1994) also confirmed the relationship between subjective norms and the intention to use a system.

- (2) Perceived behavioral control refers to an individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to perform a behavior (related to the availability of necessary resources, knowledge, and opportunities to adopt the technology). Subsequent studies by Herrero Crespo & Del Bosque (2010) also support this argument.
- (3) Consumers' attitude toward performing the behavior is measured by the individual consumer's beliefs and evaluations of the outcomes of that behavior. When consumers have confidence in the product or service, they are more likely to develop the intention to use the firm's product or service. Consumers' attitudes are influenced by their *perceived usefulness* and *perceived ease of use* of the product.

2.3. Proposed Research Model and Hypotheses

Based on prior studies and theoretical frameworks, and grounded in the Combined Theory of Planned Behavior (C-TAM-TPB), the research team proposes the following research model:

Figure 4: Proposed research model

Source: Compiled and proposed by the research team

Research Hypotheses

- Hypothesis H1: Perceived usefulness positively influences the attitude of consumers in Hanoi toward choosing office fashion.
- Hypothesis H2: Perceived ease of use positively influences the attitude of consumers in Hanoi toward purchasing office fashion.
- Hypothesis H3: Attitude positively influences the purchasing behavior of office fashion among consumers in Hanoi.
- Hypothesis H4: Subjective norms positively influence the purchasing behavior of office fashion among consumers in Hanoi.
- Hypothesis H5: Perceived behavioral control positively influences the purchasing behavior of office fashion among consumers in Hanoi.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Primary Data Collection

Based on the theoretical framework and literature review of factors influencing consumer behavior, the proposed model incorporates five independent factors: three direct factors (consumers' attitude toward choosing office fashion, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control) and two factors (perceived usefulness of office fashion and perceived ease of use) that influence the outcome through the mediating factor consumers' attitude toward office fashion. The questionnaire was designed using a five-point Likert scale, with the following options: 1. *Strongly disagree*; 2. *Disagree*; 3. *Neutral*; 4. *Agree*; 5. *Strongly agree*.

After finalizing the questionnaire, the research team conducted a random pilot survey with 25 consumers in Hanoi. The preliminary results indicated that respondents agreed with the factors included in the model. Due to time and resource constraints, the authors employed a convenience sampling method. The sample size was determined according to the guidelines of Comrey and Lee (1992) and by reference to the rule of Hoàng Trọng & Chu Nguyễn Mộng Ngọc (2005).

With 28 observed variables to be subjected to factor analysis, the minimum required sample size was calculated as $28 \times 5 = 140$ observations. The survey targeted consumers currently employed in Hanoi. From the perspective that a larger sample size enhances the stability of the estimated effects, and based on feasibility, the research team decided to distribute $n = 300$ questionnaires.

The questionnaires were delivered directly to consumers at office fashion stores and sent online via the link: <https://forms.gle/9mJpoCcCzepDAt6bA> through customer lists provided by stores and office fashion brands. A total of 275 responses were collected and used by the research team as the official dataset for analysis.

3.2. Data Processing Method

A quantitative research approach was employed to process the data collected from the consumer survey conducted in Hanoi. The structural regression equation is expressed in the general form:

$$QD = a*HV + b*CCQ + c*TD (d*TU + e*DSD)$$

where QD denotes the purchase decision, HV represents perceived behavioral control, CCQ represents subjective norms, TD represents attitude, TU represents perceived usefulness, and DSD represents perceived ease of use.

SMARTPLS software was used to test the hypotheses and evaluate the impact levels of the factors.

Step 1: Evaluating Measurement Model

Evaluating measurement model based on examining values of reliability, quality of observed variable, convergence, and discriminant

- Testing the Quality of Observed Variables (Outer Loadings)

Outer Loadings of observed variables are indicators showing the degree of association between observed variables and latent variables (proxy variables). Basically, outer loadings in SMARTPLS are the square root of the absolute value of R² linear regression from the latent variables to the sub-observed variables.

Hair et al. (2016) suggest that the outer loadings should be greater than or equal to 0.708 observed variables that are quality. To make it easier to remember, the researchers rounded off the threshold to 0.7 instead of the number 0.708.

- Evaluating Reliability

Evaluating the reliability through SMARTPLS by two main indicators, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR). Composite Reliability (CR) is preferred by many researchers over Cronbach's Alpha because Cronbach's Alpha underestimates the reliability compared with CR. Chin (1998) claims that in exploratory research CR must be over 0.6. For confirmed studies, the 0.7 threshold is the appropriate level of CR (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013). Other researchers agree that 0.7 is the appropriate threshold for the vast majority of cases such as Hair et al. (2010), and Bagozzi & Yi (1988).

Thus, the reliability through SMARTPLS is shown by Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012); Composite Reliability CR ≥ 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988).

- Testing Convergence

Evaluating Convergence on SMARTPLS is based on Ave (Average Variance Extracted). Hock & Ringle (2010) claim that a scale reaches a convergence value if AVE reaches 0.5 or higher. This level of 0.5 (50%) means that the average latent variable will explain at least 50% of the variation of each sub-observed variable. Thus, convergence is evaluated by Average Variance Extracted AVE ≥ 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010).

- Testing Discriminant Validity

Discriminant value is used to consider whether a research variable is really different from other research variables in the model. To evaluate the discriminant validity, Sarstedt & et al (2014) said that considering two criteria including cross-loadings and the measurement of Fornell and Larcker (1981). Cross-loading coefficients are often the first approach to evaluating the discriminant validity of indicators (observed variables) (Hair, Hult, et al., 2017). The load factor of the observed variable (indicator) linked in the factor (latent variable) should be greater than any of its cross-load factors (its correlation) in the other factors. Fornell and Larcker (1981) recommend that discriminant is ensured when the square root of AVE for each latent variable is higher than all correlations between latent variables. In addition, Henseler & et al (2015) used simulation studies to demonstrate that discriminant validity is better evaluated by the HTMT index that they developed.

With the HTMT index, Garson (2016) said that the discriminant validity between two latent variables is guaranteed when the HTMT index is less than 1. Henseler & et al (2015) propose that if this value is below 0.9, the discriminant validity will be guaranteed. Meanwhile, Clark & Watson (1995) and Kline (2015) used a stricter standard threshold of 0.85. SMARTPLS preferred a threshold of 0.85 in the evaluation.

- Testing Multicollinearity

In this study, the author uses a scale related to multicollinearity as a variance magnification factor (VIF). Very high levels of multicollinearity are indicated by VIF values ≥ 5 ; the model does not have multicollinearity when VIF indicators < 5 (Hair et al., 2016).

Step 2: Evaluating Structural Model

After evaluating the satisfactory measurement model, evaluate the structural model through the impact relationship, path coefficient, R squared, and f squared.

- Evaluating Impactful Relationships

To evaluate impact relationships, use the results of Bootstrap analysis. Based mainly on two columns (1) Original Sample (normalized impact factor) and (2) P Values (sig value compared to 0.05 significance level).

- Original Sample: Standardized impact factor of the original data. SMARTPLS have no unstandardized impact factor.
- Sample Mean: The average standardized impact factor of all samples from Bootstrap.
- Standard Deviation: Standard deviation of the standardized impact factor (according to the original sample).
- T Statistics: Test value t (test student the meaning of the impact).
- P Values: The significance level of the T Statistics. This significance level is considered with comparative thresholds such as 0.05, 0.1, or 0.01 (usually used as 0.05).

Evaluating the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable by R² coefficient (R square). To evaluate the R² coefficient, we will use the results of the PLS Algorithm analysis. The R² value evaluates the predictive accuracy of the model and shows the level of interpretation of the independent variable for the dependent variable. R square is between 0 and 1, the closer to 1 indicates the more independent variables that account for the dependent variable (Hair, Hult, et al, 2017). In addition, to assess the influence level of each factor, the research team calculated the *range* and the *mean value* for each factor and determined which response category the mean score fell into. The range was calculated as:

$$\text{Range} = (\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}) / n = (5 - 1) / 5 = 0.8$$

The evaluation thresholds based on the mean score were defined as follows:

- + 1.00 – 1.80: Strongly disagree
- + 1.81 – 2.60: Disagree
- + 2.61 – 3.40: Neutral
- + 3.41 – 4.20: Agree
- + 4.21 – 5.00: Strongly agree

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Survey Respondents

A total of 275 valid questionnaires were collected from consumers in Hanoi, comprising 249 female respondents (90.5%) and 26 male respondents (9.5%). Since the survey was conducted using a convenient random sampling method, the higher level of interest and willingness to respond among female consumers resulted in a gender imbalance in the sample.

Figure 5: Gender of Survey Respondents

Source: Survey results

Regarding consumers' age, the research focused on individuals currently studying and working in Hanoi. Among the 275 respondents, 168 were under 25 years old (61%), 74 were aged 25–30 (27%), 31 were aged 30–35 (11%), and 2 were aged 36–45 (1%). These results provide an overview of the age distribution of consumers in the sample.

Figure 6: Age Distribution of the Research Sample

Source: Survey results

Regarding average monthly income, the research continued to focus on consumers currently working in Hanoi. Among the 275 respondents, the majority (183 respondents, 67%) reported an average income of under 10 million VND. A total of 56 consumers (20%) had an income between 10–15 million VND. The proportions of respondents earning between 15–20 million VND and over 20 million VND were roughly equal, at 6% and 7%, respectively. These results provide an overview of the income distribution of consumers in the sample.

Figure 7: Income Distribution of the Research Sample

Source: Survey results

Regarding consumers' shopping locations, among the 275 respondents, 152 consumers (55%) reported purchasing at fashion stores; 112 consumers (40.7%) preferred purchasing from online shops; and 11 consumers (4.3%) chose to shop at shopping malls. These results provide an overview of where consumers most frequently purchase office fashion. The findings also reaffirm that e-commerce is gradually developing, and online shopping is becoming increasingly prevalent.

Figure 8: Shopping Locations of the Research Sample

Source: Survey results

Regarding the average expenditure per office fashion purchase, among the 275 respondents, 56 consumers (20%) reported spending less than 500,000 VND per purchase; 72 consumers (26%) spent between 500,000–1,000,000 VND; 134 consumers (49%) spent between 1,000,000–2,000,000 VND; and 13 consumers (5%) spent more than 2,000,000 VND per purchase. These findings provide an overview of the typical expenditure levels of consumers per office fashion shopping occasion.

Figure 9: Expenditure Levels of the Research Sample

Source: Survey results

4.2. Test Results

4.2.1. Evaluation of the Quality of Observed Variables in the Measurement Model

4.2.1.1. Assessment of Observed Variable Quality

The quality of the observed variables was assessed through the *outer loadings*, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Outer Loadings of Factors Influencing Office Fashion Purchase Behavior in Hanoi

	CCQ	SD	HU	HV	QD	TD
CCQ1	0.861					
CCQ2	0.813					
CCQ3	0.850					
CCQ4	0.870					
CCQ5	0.852					
SD1		0.828				
SD2		0.861				
SD3		0.893				
SD4		0.718				
HU1			0.832			
HU2			0.875			
HU3			0.857			
HU4			0.852			
HV1				0.741		
HV2				0.720		
HV3				0.812		
HV4				0.745		
HV5				0.793		
QD1					0.886	
QD2					0.889	
QD3					0.868	
QD4					0.939	
QD5					0.910	
TD1						0.850
TD2						0.830
TD3						0.844
TD4						0.874
TD5						0.804

Source: Test results by the research team

The results in *Table 1* show that the outer loadings of all observed variables influencing consumers' office fashion purchase behavior in Hanoi are greater than 0.7 (Hair et al., 2016), indicating that the observed variables are statistically significant.

4.2.1.2. Reliability Testing of the Measurement Scales

The reliability of the measurement scales for the factors influencing office fashion purchase behavior of consumers in Hanoi was evaluated in the PLS - SEM framework

Using two main indicators: *Cronbach's Alpha* and *Composite Reliability (CR)*.

Table 2: Reliability Coefficients (Cronbach's Alpha) and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
CCQ	0.905	0.915	0.928	0.722
HU	0.877	0.882	0.915	0.729
HV	0.829	0.876	0.874	0.582
QD	0.937	0.939	0.952	0.801
SD	0.845	0.861	0.896	0.685
TD	0.896	0.898	0.923	0.707

Source: Test results by the research team

According to *Table 2*, the reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha yielded the following results: *Subjective Norms (CCQ)* achieved 0.905; *Perceived Ease of Use (SD)* achieved 0.845; *Perceived Usefulness of Office Fashion (HU)* achieved 0.877; *Perceived Behavioral Control (HV)* achieved 0.829; *Consumers' Attitude toward Office Fashion (TD)* achieved 0.896; and *Consumers' Office Fashion Purchase Behavior (QD)* achieved 0.937. Thus, all measurement scales satisfied the threshold of > 0.7 (DeVellis, 2012) and did not violate any criteria requiring variable elimination; therefore, no variable was excluded, and the scales are deemed reliable. The Composite Reliability (CR) of all observed variables was also greater than 0.7 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988), as shown in *Table 2*. Accordingly, the measurement scales are reliable, analytically meaningful, and were retained for subsequent factor analyses.

4.2.1.3. Convergent Validity

According to the data analysis results presented in *Table 2*, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each factor was as follows: *Subjective Norms (CCQ)* reached 0.781; *Perceived Ease of Use (SD)* reached 0.685; *Perceived Usefulness (HU)* reached 0.729; *Perceived Behavioral Control (HV)* reached 0.582; *Consumers' Attitude (TD)* reached 0.707; and *Decision Behavior (QD)* reached 0.801. Therefore, the AVE for all factors was greater than 0.5 (Hock & Ringle, 2010), indicating that the model satisfies the conditions for convergent validity.

4.2.1.4. Discriminant Validity and Multicollinearity Assessment

The results in *Table 3* regarding the Fornell–Larcker criterion for the research model of factors influencing consumers' office fashion purchase decisions in Hanoi indicate that the factors *Subjective Norms*, *Perceived Ease of Use*, *Perceived Usefulness*, and *Attitude* all satisfy the condition of discriminant validity, as all square roots of AVE values on the diagonal are greater than their corresponding off-diagonal correlation values. For the factor *Perceived Behavioral Control*, the square root of AVE on the diagonal is very close to one off-diagonal value; however, the difference is minimal, and discriminant validity is still ensured. Therefore, in terms of discriminant validity, both criteria — cross-loading and the Fornell–Larcker criterion — are satisfied.

Table 3: Fornell–Larcker Criterion of the Research Model on Factors Influencing Office Fashion Purchase Decisions

	CCQ	HU	HV	QD	SD	TD
CCQ	0.850					
HU	0.524	0.854				
HV	0.708	0.599	0.763			
QD	0.664	0.643	0.763	0.895		
SD	0.624	0.520	0.753	0.545	0.828	
TD	0.774	0.697	0.695	0.654	0.737	0.841

Source: Test results by the research team

Multicollinearity Assessment

The test results show that the *Inner VIF* values, which assess multicollinearity among the latent variables, are all below 3, indicating that no multicollinearity is present.

4.2.2. Results of Impact Assessment Using the Structural Model

4.2.2.1. Evaluation of Influential Relationships

The relationships and impact levels of the factors influencing office fashion purchase behavior in Hanoi, as analyzed using SmartPLS, are illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Factors Influencing Office Fashion Purchase Behavior in Hanoi

Source: Test results using SmartPLS by the research team

The results of the Bootstrap analysis assessing the influential relationships are presented in Table 4.

Accordingly, all relationships among the factors have *p-values* < 0.05, indicating that these factors are statistically significant and demonstrate positive relationships with office fashion purchase behavior in Hanoi. (*Hypotheses H1, H2, H3, H4, and H5 are all accepted.*)

Table 4: Path Coefficients of the Structural Model

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
CCQ -> QD	0.164	0.166	0.074	2.229	0.026
HU -> TD	0.430	0.438	0.072	6.002	0.000
HV -> QD	0.543	0.547	0.058	9.441	0.000
SD -> TD	0.543	0.505	0.067	7.616	0.000
TD -> QD	0.149	0.146	0.076	1.966	0.049

Source: Test results using SMARTPLS by the research team

Based on the test results, the regression equation is presented as follows:

$$QD=0.555*HV + 0.148CCQ + 0.147*TD (0.517*DSD+0.431*HU)$$

4.2.2.2. Assessment of the Overall Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The results of the PLS Algorithm analysis yielded the R^2 value, which reflects the explanatory power of the independent variables over the dependent variable. The R^2 coefficient (R-square value) measures the overall goodness-of-fit of the model to the data (i.e., the model's explanatory capability).

According to Hair et al. (2010), R-square values of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 are suggested as thresholds for high, moderate, or low explanatory power, respectively.

Table 5: Summary of R^2 Values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
QD	0.621	0.617
TD	0.678	0.675

Source: Test results by the research team

The adjusted R^2 for the variable QD was found to be 0.617, indicating that the independent variables in the model explain 61.7% of the variance in the dependent variable QD.

Thus, the remaining 38.3% is attributable to systematic error and other factors not included in the model.

Similarly, the adjusted R^2 for the variable TD was 0.675, showing that the independent variables explain 67.5% of the variance in TD.

The remaining 32.5% is due to other factors not accounted for in the model or random error.

4.2.3. Descriptive Statistics Results

Figure 11: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Office Fashion Purchase Decision of Consumers in Hanoi” (QD)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The survey results show that the observed variable “I will invite friends and colleagues to buy office fashion whenever needed or when an opportunity arises (QD2)” attained a mean score of 3.3, and “I regularly update office fashion trends before making a purchase decision (QD5)” attained a mean score of 3.39. Respondents’ assessments of these items fell within the “Neutral” category. Next, the observed variable “Choosing to buy office fashion is the right decision for me (QD4)” achieved a mean score of 3.45, “I choose office fashion as the primary attire in my work environment (QD3)” had a mean score of 3.51, and “I purchase office fashion based on a specific plan for my workplace (QD1)” had a mean score of 3.55. These results fall within the “Agree” category. This indicates that most surveyed consumers expressed positive views regarding their choice to purchase office fashion.

Figure 12: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Perceived Behavioral Control over Office Fashion Purchase by Consumers in Hanoi” (HV)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The results show that only the observed variable “I have sufficient information to make a decision to purchase office fashion (HV5)” received a mean score of 3.25, with

respondents assessing this item as “Neutral.” The remaining variables— “I am confident in my ability to choose office fashion that suits me (HV1)” with a mean of 3.46, “I have sufficient financial means to purchase office fashion according to my organization’s standards (HV3)” with 3.72, “I know where to buy office fashion (HV4)” with 3.83, and “I have enough time to purchase office fashion according to my organization’s standards (HV2)” with 3.99—were all assessed within the “Agree” category. These findings indicate that most consumers in Hanoi have confidence in their own ability to engage in the behavior of purchasing office fashion.

Figure 13: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Subjective Norms” (CCQ)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The results show that all observed variables—“Friends and colleagues advise me to use office fashion (CCQ1)” with a mean of 3.4, “Social media influences my decision to use office fashion (CCQ4)” with 3.41, “My business partners all use office fashion (CCQ3)” with 3.45, “My organization requires and encourages me to wear office fashion according to the prescribed standard (CCQ5)” with 3.47, and “My family advises me to use office fashion at work (CCQ2)” with 3.59—were all assessed in the “Agree” category. This indicates that factors such as friends, news and advertising, social media, information from one’s organization, and family exert a strong influence.

Figure 14: Attitude toward Office Fashion (TD)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The results show that the observed variables— “I have positive feelings when wearing office fashion (TD4)” with a mean of 3.59, “Office fashion is my top choice when shopping for clothing (TD5)” with 3.63, “I feel comfortable and satisfied when wearing office fashion (TD2)” with 3.74, “I believe investing in office fashion makes me more confident (TD3)” with 3.76, and “Office fashion is necessary to maintain a professional image (TD1)” with 3.81—were all assessed within the “Agree” category. This indicates that the majority of surveyed consumers hold a positive attitude toward the behavior of purchasing office fashion.

Figure 15: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Perceived Ease of Use” (SD)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The results show that the observed variables— “It is easy to find office fashion products on online shopping platforms (SD4)” with a mean of 3.71, “I feel that office fashion is easy to wash and maintain (SD2)” with 3.88, “I find office fashion easy to wear and mix-and-match (SD1)” with 3.89, and “I find office fashion suitable for many body types and sizes (SD3)” with 3.94—were all assessed within the “Agree” category. This suggests that the majority of consumers perceive office fashion as easy to use.

Based on the descriptive statistics of these factors, the author concludes that consumers in Hanoi have a high demand for office fashion. Accordingly, the author proposes solutions and recommendations to further attract consumers.

Figure 16: Mean Value of the Measurement Scale for the Factor “Perceived Usefulness” (HU)

Source: Compiled and calculated from survey results

The results show that the observed variables— “Wearing office fashion helps me feel more confident at work (HU2)” with a mean of 3.68, “I believe that office fashion meets the demands of convenience and professionalism in the workplace (HU4)” with 3.73, “I think that wearing office fashion brings benefits and value to my job (HU1)” with 3.86, and “Office fashion is suitable for many situations, not just in the office (HU3)” with 3.89— were all assessed within the “Agree” category. This indicates that most consumers hold a positive perception of the usefulness of office fashion.

5. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Discussion of Research Findings

The test results show that among the factors included in the model, with 95% confidence, the factor Perceived Behavioral Control (HV) has a strong positive correlation with office fashion purchase behavior ($t = 9.441$; $p < 0.05$), with an impact coefficient of 0.543. This means that when consumers’ perceived behavioral control increases by one unit, their decision to purchase office fashion increases by 0.543 units. Next is the factor Subjective Norms (CCQ) with an impact coefficient of 0.164, meaning that when consumers’ subjective norms increase by one unit, their decision to purchase office fashion increases by 0.164 units. The factor Perceived Ease of Use affects consumers’ attitude with an impact of 0.543, and Perceived Usefulness influences consumers’ attitude with an impact of 0.430.

The descriptive statistics also align with the test results. Most surveyed consumers tend to choose to purchase office fashion; however, they are not yet ready to recommend or encourage friends and family to use similar products. Most consumers believe that purchasing office fashion in Hanoi is fairly convenient and accessible thanks to the development of retail stores, e-commerce platforms, and online sales channels. Consumers also recognize the usefulness of office fashion—not only does it make them appear more professional, but it also contributes to projecting a serious and appropriate image in the workplace.

Moreover, when consumers have sufficient product information, feel in control when selecting styles and sizes, and find the options suited to their financial means, they are more likely to make purchasing decisions. However, the survey results also reveal differences in demand and purchase frequency across different consumer groups. Some consumers tend to shop seasonally or during promotions, while younger customers prioritize diversity, trendiness, and reasonable prices. This implies that businesses must be more flexible in product design, pricing strategies, and channel expansion to cater to each customer segment effectively.

5.2. Recommendations

Enhance the online shopping experience: With 40.7% of consumers in the sample opting for online shopping, businesses should invest in e-commerce platforms such as Shopee, Lazada, or their own branded websites. Providing detailed product information (materials,

sizes, styling guidance), flexible return policies, and fast delivery services will help consumers feel more confident in making purchasing decisions.

Strengthen promotional programs: Discount campaigns, gifts, or special offers for loyal customers—particularly during major holidays such as Tet—can stimulate purchasing behavior. For example, offering bundled office attire packages at preferential prices could appeal to the segment of consumers earning less than 5 million VND per month (61.1% of the sample). **Develop social media campaigns:** Leverage platforms like Facebook and Zalo to run advertising campaigns targeting younger customers (20–25 years old), emphasizing the value of wearing office fashion to express confidence and professionalism. For example, short videos on office outfit styling or success stories highlighting professional images can create emotional connections with consumers. **Increase variety in styles and sizes:** Offer products tailored to the body shape of Vietnamese consumers while diversifying colors (favoring neutral tones such as white, black, navy) and designs to meet the preferences of different age groups, particularly the 20–25 segment that tends to prioritize modern styles.

6. CONCLUSION

This study examined five factors (independent variables) influencing office fashion purchase decisions, including three factors with direct effects and two factors influencing through a mediating variable. The findings demonstrate that all five factors considered have an impact on consumers' decisions to purchase office fashion. The study also reveals an increasing tendency among Hanoi consumers to purchase office fashion, particularly among groups seeking to express a professional and polished image in the workplace. Moreover, factors such as brand, product quality, convenience, social influence, and media information also play an important role in the purchasing decision-making process. The research proposes several recommendations: enhancing the online shopping experience and diversifying distribution channels; leveraging social influence through KOLs, media campaigns, and workplace incentives; designing practical, easy-to-coordinate products suited to Vietnamese body shapes and aesthetics; building brands that reflect Vietnamese cultural identity and enhance trustworthiness; as well as applying personalized marketing strategies and promoting sustainable office fashion. This study provides valuable insights into the factors influencing office fashion purchase decisions among consumers in Hanoi and proposes solutions to attract and encourage greater adoption of office fashion.

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